

TRITERPENES OF *ALSTONIA SCHOLARIS* R.Br.

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α -Amyrin acetate and lupeol acetate have been isolated as the major triterpenes of the bark of *Alstonia scholaris*.

In connection with our work on the alkaloids of *Alstonia scholaris* R. Br. involving extraction of large quantities of dita-bark, we obtained considerable amounts of a neutral product, which after several crystallisations from a mixture of ethanol and ether afforded a colorless crystalline product having a constant m.p. 160°. The product was found to be non-nitrogenous.

It may be mentioned in this connection that Jobst and Hesse (*Annalen*, 1875, 178, 49) obtained the following non-nitrogenous substances from the bark of *A. scholaris*: (a) Echikautschin (amorphous); (b) Echicerin, $C_{30}H_{48}O_2$, m.p. 157°, $[\alpha]_D + 63.75^\circ$; (c) Echitin, $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$, m.p. 170°, $[\alpha]_D + 75.25^\circ$; (d) Echitein, $C_{42}H_{70}O_2$, m.p. 195°, $[\alpha]_D + 85.4^\circ$; (e) Echiretin, $C_{35}H_{56}O_2$, (amorphous). Ultee (*Chem. Weekblad.*, 1914, 11, 456) reported the presence of α - and β -amyryns in the latex of *A. scholaris*. Goodson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 2626) isolated two lactones from the bark of the same plant. One of these was reported to have the molecular formula $C_9H_{14}O_3$.

In view of the anomalous position with regard to the non-nitrogenous constituents of the bark of *A. scholaris*, a detailed investigation was undertaken by the present authors with the product melting at 160°, described above. After repeated careful chromatography of the product over alumina it was ultimately possible to separate it into two pure constituents: products (A) and (B).

Product (A) had m.p. 224-25°, $[\alpha]_D^{29} + 80^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), molecular formula $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ with one acetyl group and no active hydrogen. On hydrolysis with methanolic potassium hydroxide it gave a product, m.p. 184°, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 84^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), molecular formula $C_{30}H_{50}O$, identical with α -amyrin, thus establishing the identity of the product (A) with α -amyrin acetate. On benzylation of the hydrolysed product of m.p. 184°, α -amyrin benzoate was obtained, m.p. 198°, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 92^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), molecular formula $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$.

Product (B) had m.p. 215-16°, $[\alpha]_D^{28} + 40^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), molecular formula $C_{32}H_{52}O_2$ with one acetyl group and no active hydrogen. Mixed m.p. with product (A) is 175-77°, indicating that the two products are different. On hydrolysis with methanolic potassium hydroxide it gave a product, m.p. 212-13°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 22.6^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), molecular formula $C_{30}H_{50}O$, identical with lupeol. Thus, product (B) is lupeol acetate. On benzylation of the hydrolysed product of m.p. 212-13°, lupeol benzoate, m.p. 260°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 60.4^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$), molecular formula $C_{37}H_{54}O_2$, was obtained.

It is thus clear that the bark of *A. scholaris* contains α -amyrin acetate and lupeol acetate. According to our experience fractional crystallisation is of very little help in the separation of the constituents in such cases, and this may explain the difficulties encountered by previous workers in proper purification and separation of the constituents. It is of interest to note in this connection that many workers isolate these triterpenes after saponification, following the standard method for isolation of sterols. In such cases it is difficult to find out whether the triterpenes occur in the free state or as any of their derivatives in the plant.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of Triterpenes of A. scholaris (Dita-bark).—The air-dried, powdered bark of *A. scholaris* was extracted in a percolator in 6 kg. lots with 96% ethanol by cold percolation (8-10 drainings were necessary). The extracts were concentrated to a small volume and kept for about two weeks. The solid product separating was filtered and washed with 70% ethanol (~3% crude yield). It was dried and then dissolved in sufficient ether, and filtered. The crystalline residue (yield ~ 2%) obtained from the filtered solution was crystallised from ethanol containing a little ether, m.p. 140-45°. After repeated crystallisations from the same solvent mixture and on treatment with charcoal, a product, m.p. 160°, was obtained in colorless crystals. It was found to be non-nitrogenous and neutral in character. It did not respond to the Liebermann-Burchard test for sterols.

Chromatography of the product (m.p. 160°).—The product (m.p. 160°; 2.5 g.) was dissolved in petroleum ether (b. p. 40-60°) (20 c.c.) and chromatographed through a column of Brockmann alumina (diam. 4 cm × length 32 cm), the column being successively eluted with (i) petroleum ether (40-60)°, (ii) benzene, and (iii) absolute ethanol. The results are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Fractions.	Volume collected.	Wt. of residue.	M.P.	Fractions.	Volume collected.	Wt. of residue.	M.P.
		Eluent: Petroleum ether.			Eluent: Benzene.		
I	20 c.c.	0.09 g.	Yellow oil	VI	100 c.c.	0.1 g.	Amorphous
II	50	0.8	Amorphous	VII	100	0.07	"
					Eluent: Ethanol.		
III	100	0.9	163-80	VIII	100	0.15	"
IV	100	0.2	170-95°	IX	100	0.02	"
V	100	0.1	202-205°				

Fractions II, III and, IV (Table I) were rechromatographed separately over alumina using petroleum ether (40-60°) as eluent. Fraction II gave a little oil followed by a product, m.p. 212-14° (product A), and another, m.p. 170-80°, which appeared to be a mixture. Fractions III and IV behaved similarly and gave product (A), m.p. 215-16° in the first portion, a product, m.p. 168-69°, in the middle portion and a third product, m.p. 205-206° (product B), in the last portion. Fraction V was found to be more or less identical with product (B). The product of m.p. 168-69° crystallised in colorless needles from a mixture of ethanol and ether, but even after repeated treatment in this way no further change in the m.p. could be observed. On rechromatography, however, using a long column it could be separated into product (A) in the first portion and product (B) in the last portion, with a small amount of an intermediate fraction, which was evidently a mixture of the two. The overall yields of product (A) and product (B) are 0.8% and 0.7% respectively on the basis of air-dried bark.

Product (A), α -Amyrin Acetate.—The product (A) after several crystallisations from a mixture of ethanol and ether was obtained in colorless plates, m.p. 224-25°, $[\alpha]_{D}^{25} + 80^{\circ}$ (CHCl₃), identical with α -amyrin acetate. It does not contain any active H but contains one acetyl group. [Found: C, 82.2, 82.0; H, 11.1, 11.0; CH₃CO, 11.3, 8.5; M.W., 450, 462. Calc. for C₃₀H₅₀O₃: C, 82.0; H, 11.1; CH₃CO (for one), 9.2%; M.W., 468].

α -Amyrin.—A purified specimen of product (A) (0.5 g.) was dissolved in methanol (100 c.c.) by refluxing on a steam bath. KOH (5 g.), dissolved in least amount of water, was then added and the refluxing continued for 7 hours. After evaporation of ethanol with addition of water,

the separated solid product was taken up in ether, and crystallised repeatedly from a mixture of ethanol and ether, when colorless needles were obtained, m.p. 184°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 84^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical with α -amyrin. (Found: C, 84.4, 84.6; H, 11.7, 11.6; active H, 0.32, 0.26. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.4; H, 11.8; active H, 0.23%). The alkaline mother-liquor obtained above on distillation after acidification gave a distillate, which was found to contain acetic acid.

It gave α -amyrin benzoate on benzoylation with benzoyl chloride and pyridine in the usual way (Chakravarti and Dutta, this *Journal*, 1952, 29, 374) and crystallisation from a mixture of benzene and ethanol in prisms, m.p. 198°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 92^\circ$ (CHCl_3). (Found: C, 83.6, 83.5; H, 10.1; 10.2; benzoyl, 18.8. Calc. for $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$: C, 83.7; H, 10.2; benzoyl, 19.8%).

Product (B), lupeol acetate, was obtained in colorless needles after several crystallisations from a mixture of ethanol and ether, m.p. 215-16°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 40^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical with lupeol acetate. It does not contain any active H. [Found: C, 82.1, 82.2; H, 11.0, 11.1; CH_3CO , 8.9; M.W., 460. Calc. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_2$: C, 82.0; H, 11.1; CH_3CO (for one), 9.2%; M.W., 468].

Lupeol.—A purified specimen of product (B) (0.5 g.) was refluxed with methanolic KOH (100 c.c.) (ca. 5%) for 7 hours on a steam bath. On working up as in the case of α -amyrin, a crystalline product was obtained; it was possible to detect the presence of acetic acid in the alkaline mother-liquor. After several crystallisations from a mixture of ethanol and ether, the product was obtained in colorless needles, m.p. 212-13°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 22.6^\circ$ (CHCl_3), identical with lupeol. A mixture of the two products, α -amyrin and lupeol, as obtained above, melts at 163-65°. (Found: C, 84.5, 84.6; H, 11.6, 11.8; active H, 0.28. Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}$: C, 84.4; 11.8; active H, 0.23%).

On benzoylation of the above product and crystallisation as in the case of α -amyrin, lupeol benzoate was obtained in colorless plates, m.p. 259-60°, $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 60.4^\circ$ (CHCl_3). (Found: C, 83.6, 83.7; H, 10.2, 10.3; benzoyl, 19.2. Calc. for $\text{C}_{37}\text{H}_{54}\text{O}_2$: C, 83.7; H, 10.2; benzoyl, 19.8%).